

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

ARTEMIS

Deliverable 2.2 & 2.3 Annex

AE systems yield stability under climatic stress
Country specific report
Southern Italy (Metaponto, Basilicata)

Due date of deliverable: M57

Actual submission date: 31.10.2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 862695

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Program title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Programm website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Project title: Agro-ecological strategies for promoting climate change Mitigation and Adaptation by enhancing soil ecosystem services and sustainable crop production.

Project Acronym: EJP Soil ARTEMIS

Project website: <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/eom4soil/into-dialogue/artemis>

Start date of the project: October 1st, 2022

Project duration: 24 Months

Topic: CA4/SP3-1

Project type: Medium-sized project

Project coordinator: Klaus Jarosch, AGROSCOPE, Switzerland;

Project co-coordinator: Claudia di Bene, CREA, Italy

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	D2.2 & 2.3
DELIVERABLE TITLES:	AE systems yield stability under climatic stress - Annex
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP 2
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Identification of AE systems and soil properties that support yield stability using LTEs
DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.14038773
LICENCE	CC BY 4.0
DELIVERABLE LEADER:	CRA-W, Centre wallon de Recherches agronomiques – Belgium, Wallonie AGS, Agroscope - Switzerland
CONTRIBUTING PARTNERS:	Crea: Claudia di Bene, Gianluca Carboni, Alessandro Persiani, Vincenzo Alfano, Francesco Montemurro, Angelo Fiore, Mariangela Diacono

Analysis of yield stability and performances in the MITIORG LONG-TERM field trial in Southern Italy Report related to WP2

<https://www.crea.gov.it/>

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1. Abstract

Organic agriculture (OA) is a sustainable farming practice aimed at enhancing agro-environmental resilience. Thus, in Mediterranean area, where agricultural systems are mainly affected by climate variability and soil degradation, OA offers a potential solution to maintain soil health and cropping system resilience, without deeply compromise crop productivity. In this context, increasing agroecological soil management practices and crop diversity can be considered among the most important tools to re-design agricultural systems. This study aimed at showing how powerful is the sustainability assessment of agroecological practices by converting crops yield into energy outputs, in diversified horticultural systems. Particularly, the study evaluates the effects of different agroecological strategies on crop stability of vegetable crops tested in a long-term field experiment (LTE) conducted in southern Italy. The LTE is characterized by a soil hydraulic arrangement in ridges, strips and the use (with different management options) of cover crops within horticulture cash crops rotations carried out to assess Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Measures in Organic Vegetable Systems (MITIORG field experiment). In this study, multivariate analysis techniques were applied to analyze the interactions between MITIORG agroecological strategies adopted in the field trial and environment. The crop performance and yield stability outputs (expressed as yield energy output equivalents) of the whole crop sequence were evaluated and analyzed considering the site-specific meteorological data in the horticultural cropping cycles, from autumn-winter 2014–15 to autumn-winter 2020-21.

Preliminary results suggest that it is possible to redesign more sustainable and diversified farming systems to enhance the provisioning of ecosystem services and the resilience of agroecosystem. Thus, more attention should be paid to try increasing the stability of yield, since the frequency of heavy events is increased in the last years. Thus, the agroecological management practices adopted on the flat strips such as GM-ORG and RC2-ORG or on the ridges such as ASC2-ORG and ASC1-CT can increase the yield energy stability of the crop sequence, because they have the potential to achieve good performances and resilience of the system, especially when the climate conditions are not optimal, or extreme climate events occur.

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2. Introduction

Organic agriculture (OA) is a sustainable farming strategy aimed at enhancing agro-environmental sustainability without deeply compromising crop productivity. In the Mediterranean region, where agricultural systems are mainly affected by climate variability and soil degradation, OA offers a potential solution to maintain soil health and cropping system resilience, without deeply compromise crop productivity. In this context, increasing agroecological soil management practices and crop diversity can be considered among the most important tools to re-design agricultural systems. This study aimed at showing how powerful is the sustainability assessment of agroecological practices by converting crops yield into energy outputs, in diversified horticultural systems. Particularly, the study evaluates the effects of different agroecological strategies on crop stability of vegetable crops tested in a long-term field experiment (LTE) conducted in southern Italy. The LTE is characterized by a soil hydraulic arrangement in ridges, strips and the use (with different management options) of cover crops within horticulture cash crops rotations carried out to assess Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Measures in Organic Vegetable Systems (MITIORG field experiment). In this study, multivariate analysis techniques were applied to analyze the interactions between MITIORG agroecological strategies adopted in the field trial and environment. The crop performance and yield stability outputs (expressed as yield energy output equivalents) of the whole crop sequence were evaluated and analyzed considering the site-specific meteorological data in the horticultural cropping cycles, from autumn-winter 2014–15 to autumn-winter 2020-21.

3. Material and Methods

3.1. Description of the MITIORG experimental design and long-term field trial

MITIORG is a multi-year field trial of about 2500 m² that was established in 2014 at the experimental farm “Azienda Sperimentale Metaponto” of the Research Centre for Agriculture and Environment, Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA-AA), located in Metaponto (MT), Southern Italy (lat. 40° 24' N; long. 16° 48' E; 8 m a.s.l.).

Soil is clayey and poorly drained with a superficial water table, classified as “Typic Epiaquerts”. Additional information and details on the main chemical and physical properties along the soil profile are reported in Di Bene et al. (2022).

Climate is classified as “accentuated thermo-Mediterranean”. characterized by hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters. Rainfall is highly seasonal, with most precipitations occurring during the winter months, with extended periods of drought in late spring and summer. In the last decades, during autumn and winter periods, extreme precipitation events (resulting in temporary soil flooding) frequently occurred, which greatly affected vegetable productivity and potential profitability of local farming enterprises. The long-term (1981–2023) data collected from the nearby weather station showed that annual minimum and maximum temperature ranged from 8.5 to 11.6°C and from 19.8 to 23.4°C, respectively. The annual precipitation ranged from 310 to 782 mm and potential evapotranspiration ranged from 1030 to 1313. These climate conditions can be considered as representative of the agricultural areas of Southern Italy.

The MITIORG field trial was setup to adapt local organic vegetable systems to extreme winter rainfall events, considering the hypothesis that the adoption of combined agroecological practices - as

adaptation and mitigation measures - may increase the resilience of a typical Mediterranean organic vegetable system to cope with climate change effects.

The field trial was designed considering the combination of the following agroecological practices:

1. **Soil surface shaping**: consisting of a ridge-furrow system in which vegetables are cultivated both on three convex-shaped ridges (each 2.5 m wide) and in four flat strips (each 2.5 m wide) between them. The ridge-furrow system based on soil surface shaping allows to increase the rooting depth layers in periods with high rainfall, eliminating the risk of water stagnation and making easier the lateral outflow of excess water.

2. **Crop rotations**: on the ridges, the rotation includes both winter (cauliflower, *Brassica oleracea* L., var. Triumphans; fennel, *Foeniculum vulgare* Mill., var. Tiberio) and summer cash crops (tomato, *Solanum lycopersicum* L., var. Donald), whereas in the flat strips, only summer cash crops (tomato, zucchini, *Cucurbita pepo* L., var. President; lettuce, *Lactuca sativa* L., var. Romana) are cultivated. Rotation in the flat strips was designed to avoid cash crop cultivation during autumn–winter period because the strips can be temporary waterlogged and flooded by heavy rains in these months.

3. **Introduction of cover crops as agroecological service crops (ASCs)**: on the ridges, a leguminous crop (burr medic, *Medicago polymorpha* L.; or crimson clover, *Trifolium incarnatum* L.) is intercropped with a winter cash crop and terminated before the subsequent summer cash crop planting. On the flat strips, ASCs pure or as mixture of leguminous and non-leguminous winter crops (i.e., vetch, *Vicia sativa* L. – barley, *Hordeum vulgare* L.; rice, *Oryza sativa* L.; field pea, *Pisum sativum* L.; rapeseed, *Brassica napus* L.; rice–faba bean, *Vicia faba minor* L.—rapeseed; vetch – oats, *Avena sativa* L.; oats-rice), potentially resistant to temporary water logging, are cultivated in the winter-rainy period as break crops.

4. **ASC management**: on the ridges, the ASCs are managed as living mulch (LM), whereas on the flat strips, they are chopped and ploughed into the soil as green manure (GM) or flattened by no-tillage roller crimper termination practice (RC), before transplanting the next summer cash crop.

5. **Organic fertilization**: implemented with commercial organic fertilizers and amendments, allowed in organic farming, to increase both the soil organic matter content and fertility in the long-term. The fertilization rate followed local, national, and European community rules. In the ASC treatments, the application of organic fertilizer was reduced considering the biological N fixation by the leguminous cover crops.

The ridges were organized in a strip-plot design, while the flat strips in a strip-split plot design. In both the ridges and flat strips three replications were tested.

Figure 1 shows a schematic arrangement of the MITIORG field trial, indicating the three ridges (R1–3) and the four flat strips (FS1–4) in which the effects of agroecological practices as adaptation and mitigation tools are assessed (Metaponto, Southern Italy). The picture shows the management of the ridges and flat strips in winter. On the ridges, cauliflower is transplanted pure (without ASCs) or intercropped with crimson clover as ASCs, managed as LM. In the flat strips, the soil is bare, or legume-winter cereal ASC mixtures are sown, terminated as GM, or flattened by RC before the transplanting of the summer cash crop.

Fig. 1: Schematic arrangement of the MITIORG field trial

Figure 2 shortly summarizes the MITIORG field trial, giving information on crop rotation, fertilization, and ASC management.

MITIORG-LTE – Southern Italy

- 2014
 - Experiment area : 2500 mq
 - Crop rotation: horticultural crops and cover crops
 - Soil surface shaping: consisting of a ridge-furrow system
- Treatments
- Cover crops termination with roller crimper or as green manure
 - Organic fertilization (on-farm composts and commercial fertilizers)

- Agroecological service crops (ASC) (No ASC; ASC terminated with roller crimper; green manured ASC)
- Organic fertilizers (on-farm compost 100%; on farm compost 40%)

IV replicates; spring summer horticultural crops

Fig. 2: Description of the MITIORG field trial

Table 1 shortly summarizes the MITIORG tested treatments in both the ridges and the flat strips.

Table 1 – List of the treatments tested in both the flat strips (FS 1-4) and ridges (R 1-3) at the MITIORG field trial

Treatment	Acronym
<u>Flat strips – FS 1-4</u>	
Cover crops terminated as green manure and compost product at farm applied	GM-CA
Cover crops terminated as green manure with no fertilization applied (used as control)	GM-CT
Cover crops terminated as green manure and commercial organic fertilizer applied	GM-ORG
No cover crops and compost product at farm applied	N-CA
No cover crops with no fertilization applied (used as control)	N-CT
No cover crops and commercial organic fertilizer applied	N-ORG
Cover crops MIX1 flattened and compost product at farm applied	RC1-CA
Cover crops MIX1 flattened with no fertilization applied (used as control)	RC1-CT
Cover crops MIX1 flattened and commercial organic fertilizer applied	RC1-ORG
Cover crops MIX2 flattened and compost product at farm applied	RC2-CA
Cover crops MIX2 flattened with no fertilization applied (used as control)	RC2-CT
Cover crops MIX2 flattened and commercial organic fertilizer applied	RC2-ORG
<u>Ridges – R1-3</u>	
Agroecological service crops (cover crops) - burr medic and compost product at farm applied	ASC1-CA
Agroecological service crops (cover crops) - burr medic with no fertilization applied (used as control)	ASC1-CT
Agroecological service crops (cover crops) - burr medic and commercial organic fertilizer applied	ASC1-ORG
Agroecological service crops (cover crops) - crimson clover and compost product at farm applied	ASC2-CA
Agroecological service crops (cover crops) - crimson clover with no fertilization applied (used as control)	ASC2-CT
Agroecological service crops (cover crops) - crimson clover and commercial organic fertilizer applied	ASC2-ORG
No cover crops and compost product at farm applied	NO-CA
No cover crops with no fertilization applied (used as control)	NO-CT
No cover crops and commercial organic fertilizer applied	NO-ORG

The main field management practices (tillage, fertilization, sowing, planting, irrigation, ASC termination, and harvesting) are reported in Di Bene et al. (2022). Additional information and details on the long-term field experiment are reported in Diacono et al. (2016, 2017, 2020).

3.2. Overview on measurements and analyses performed to assess crop stability and cropping system sustainability

Weather information

Since 1981, meteorological parameters are continuously monitored by collecting data from a nearby weather station. Meteorological data are used for estimating the influence of climate change on crop performance.

Cash crop yield determination and cover crop measurements

Since 2014, samples of cash crops and ASCs are collected to qualitatively and quantitatively analyses. During the cash crop harvest time at commercial maturity, marketable crop yield (Mg ha^{-1}), yield dry matter (%), aboveground plant residue dry matter (Mg ha^{-1}), and C yield output (i.e., C sequestered in the crop products; Mg C ha^{-1}) are determined from five randomly selected plants within a one-meter-square area in each replicate plot of both the ridges and flat strips. Moreover, the following qualitative crop parameters are determined: nitrate content (mg kg^{-1}) for cauliflower and lettuce crops, total soluble solids ($^{\circ}\text{BRIX}$) for tomato, and product size (g) for zucchini crop. The nitrate content is estimated using the Nitrachek 404 reflectometer, $^{\circ}\text{BRIX}$ parameter is determined using the Stevens and Baier procedure (1939), and the zucchini size is calculated dividing the whole selected plants production by the number of fruits. Regarding ASCs and weeds measurement, aboveground biomass dry matter (Mg kg^{-1}) and their C and N (as Mg C ha^{-1} , Mg N ha^{-1}) contents are analysed by clipping plants at ground level within a one-meter-square area at the ASC cycle termination. Particularly, three sampling areas are randomly selected in each replicate plot of both the ridges and flat strips to collect fresh aboveground biomass both of ASCs and weeds (in R3 and FS3–4) or only weeds (in R1–2 and FS1–2). All samples of ASCs, weeds, and cash crops are fractionated into two parts. One part is oven-dried for 48 h at 70°C (up to weight stabilization) to determine the dry matter content; another part was dried at 55°C to constant weight for nutrient analysis. Then, all these organic materials used as inputs to soil are analysed to determine total N, by Dumas method using the elemental analyser LECO FP 528, and total organic carbon (TOC) content by a LECO analyser (LECO RC-612), using a dry combustion method (LECO Corporation, St. Joseph, MI, USA). Total N and TOC content per hectare of biomass are calculated by multiplying the content by the whole biomass value (dry-weight basis), allowing the calculation of total N and TOC from ASCs, plant residues, and weeds added to the soil. The C sequestered in the crop products (i.e., C yield output) is calculated by using the formula reported in Diacono et al. (2020).

Selection of crop stability indices to assess cropping system sustainability

The review written by Recking et al. (2021) proposed a list of 42 stability indices and we considered it to select the most suitable indices to assess yield stability of organic vegetable crops. The selection of the best crop stability indices to assess the performance of agroecological practices and cropping system sustainability in the LTEs depends on various factors such as the specific objectives of the field trial and the agro-environmental conditions. In the last decades, numerous indices have been proposed to assess crop stability over time besides the well-known coefficient of variation (CV). Very often treatments (e.g., more frequently genotype) \times environment interaction (GEI) in multi environmental trials (METs) are statistically significant, thus the discordance of the treatment's response in each environment makes the interpretation of the data difficult. The interpretation of data obtained in METs with significant GEI was done using the multivariate techniques as effective and valid methods. Particularly, the AMMI-Based Stability Statistics (deriving from the Additive Main effects and Multiplicative Interaction (AMMI) model) and the GGE Biplot approach are the most

widely used methods in the last decades. The statistical analyses were performed using R software: for the mixed models *lme4*, *lmerTest* and *emmeans* R packages. The GGEbiplot analysis was performed using the *metan* package. In this study, crop productivity and yield stability of whole crops in rotation were assessed by yield energy that refers to the energy related to the marketable yields. The yield energy represents an energy output, calculated following the study of Persiani et al. (2023) by multiplying the products and the biomass (expressed in kg) of each crop by their coefficients of equivalent energy, derived from the literature. The yield energy stability is expressed as MJ ha⁻¹.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Performance and crop stability indices

A first analysis of yield stability has been performed using the CVs as an inverse measure of crop stability. Figures 3 and 5 show the distribution of the CVs for each agroecological practice combination, tested yearly in both flat strips and ridges, respectively. Nevertheless, these figures are not able to highlight what agroecological management strategy allows more stable yields, because it seems that crop stability depends on year and soil hydraulic arrangement. Therefore, a more complex analysis considering both productivity and crop stability was performed using mixed models. In the mixed model analyses, we considered years and replication as random factors, while other treatments were considered as fixed.

Fig. 3: Yearly distribution of coefficient of variation (CV) for each agroecological management strategy in flat strips at the MITIORG field trial

The analysis is quite limited because of few years of crop yield and productivity data available (4 years). To evaluate crop productivity and yield stability we considered the yield energy. The statistical significance of the treatments tested in the flat strips is shown in Table 2. On average, in the flat strips, the GM-ORG is the most productive treatment followed by RC2-ORG, for the 4-years of the cropping seasons considered (Table 2).

The GGE biplot analysis (Figure 4) was performed to see graphically the best agroecological management strategy for both the productivity and crop stability, as already described by Yan and Kang (2003). The green axis oriented to the right is the axis of productive environment (average year compared to the 4-years analysed). Hence, as showed in Figure 4, GM-ORG is the most productive treatment followed by RC2-ORG, other tested treatments are clustered around the origin (average productivity values) and are lower than the GM-ORG treatment (Figure 5 and Table 2. The lowest productive treatments are represented by N-CT, N-CA, and RC2-CT.

Table 2 – Mean comparison ($P=0.05$) of yield expressed in energy ($MJ\ ha^{-1}$) value of the crop sequence cultivated in the flat strips at MITIORG field trial as influenced by the tested agroecological management practices

Treatment	Yield energy value	Significance
GM-ORG	18.25	a
RC2-ORG	13.04	ab
RC2-CA	10.08	bc
GM-CT	9.04	bcd
GM-CA	8.96	bcd
RC1-ORG	8.08	bcde
N-ORG	7.09	bcde
RC1-CA	6.97	bcde
RC1-CT	6.12	cde
RC2-CT	3.16	de
N-CA	2.03	e
N-CT	1.55	e

Fig. 4: GGEbiplot of the flat strips at the MITIORG field trial

The greater the distance perpendicular (to the arrow) to the axis is, the lower the crop stability is. Therefore, GM-ORG and RC2-ORG are less stable than the other treatments but more productive (RC2-ORG in 2016 spatial proximity i.e. the angle formed between vector from 2016 to origin and RC2_ORG and origin is narrow i.e. positive correlation) and similarly GM - ORG for 2017 (practically angle 0).

Fig. 5: Yearly distribution of coefficient of variation (CV) for each agroecological management strategy in ridges at the MITIORG field trial

The statistically significance of the treatments tested in the flat strips is shown in Table 3. As expected, the worst agroecological management practices both statistically (see Table 3) and graphically (figure 6) are represented by the NO-CT and NO-CA treatments.

Table 3 – Mean comparison ($P=0.05$) of yield expressed in energy (MJ ha^{-1}) value among agroecological management practices in the ridges at MITIORG field trial

Treatment	Yield energy value	Significance
ASC2-ORG	20.14	a
ASC1-CT	19.59	ab
ASC1-ORG	17.93	abc
ASC2-CA	16.6	abc
NO-ORG	16.06	abcd
ASC1-CA	14.65	bcd
ASC2-CT	13.96	cd
NO-CA	10.9	de
NO-CT	5.84	e

Also in the ridges, this type of GGE biplot gives indications on crop productivity and stability. In this biplot the environments are arranged to the left and hence the green axis representing the axis of increasing productivity towards the left.

In this case generally, there are no big differences in stability between treatments apart from ASC1-CT which is far from the green axes.

Fig. 6: GGEbiplot of the ridges at the MITIORG field trial

As showed in Figure 6, ASC2-ORG and ASC1-CT showed the best results for the 6-year considered. However, ASC2-ORG treatment showed better results in terms of stability compared to ASC1-CT. Particularly, the good performance of ASC1-CT is mainly due to the good performance observed in the 2018 cropping season. This year is different from the others because it is in a completely different area of the biplot compared to the other cropping seasons. This data highlighted that the ASC1-ORG is to be preferred to the ASC1-CT in terms of performance and crop stability, because it is more stable over the years (closer to the green line, which has a direction to the left). The analysis of productivity and crop stability was completed by calculating other alternative indices, although each has its strengths and weaknesses. Tables 4a,b show discordance between stability indices, mainly based on CV, and more recent ones, mainly based on AMMI analysis. Results obtained basically agree with the GGE method proposed in this report.

Table 4a - Other crop energy stability indices calculated for agroecological management practices adopted on the flat strips at the MITIORG field trial. Numbers in bold indicate decreasing stability for the index considered. Per each index, the first column refers to the yield energy stability value, while the second to the stability ranking among the tested between treatments (the lowest value is the most stable; while the highest the most unstable).

Treatment	Energy (MJ ha ⁻¹)	CV		ACV		W Ecovalence		YSI		ASV		Shukla's stability variance	
		Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank	Value	Rank
GM-CA	8.96	53.8	2	63.3	6	70.4	6	14	5	2.5	9	8.2	6
GM-CT	9.04	66.0	5	58.9	4	78.1	8	11	4	2.3	7	9.2	8
GM-ORG	18.25	47.1	1	70.3	10	383.4	12	13	1	6.5	12	49.9	12
N-CA	2.03	135.8	11	68.5	9	64.6	5	19	11	2.4	8	7.4	5
N-CT	1.55	150.8	12	55.7	3	161.0	11	23	12	3.8	11	20.3	11
N-ORG	7.09	90.5	9	62.7	5	77.3	7	17	7	2.8	10	9.1	7
RC1-CA	6.97	71.1	6	55.3	2	15.1	1	10	8	1.2	2	0.8	1
RC1-CT	6.12	83.8	7	67.9	8	35.2	3	13	9	1.6	4	3.5	3
RC1-ORG	8.08	86.3	8	83.3	12	109.5	9	9	6	1.4	3	13.4	9
RC2-CA	10.08	58.8	3	33.4	1	32.4	2	4	3	1.0	1	3.1	2
RC2-CT	3.16	111.9	10	65.1	7	38.5	4	15	10	2.0	5	3.9	4
RC2-ORG	13.04	61.8	4	71.7	11	136.8	10	8	2	2.1	6	17.0	10

- CV Coefficient of variance
ACV scale-adjusted coefficient of variation
W Ecovalence Wricke's ecovalence
YSI Yield stability index
ASV AMMI stability value
Shukla's stability variance Weighted Average of Absolute Scores for AMMI analysis

Table 4b - Other crop energy stability indices calculated for agroecological practices adopted on the ridges at the MITIORG field trial. Numbers in bold indicate decreasing stability for the index considered. Per each index, the first column refers to the yield energy stability value, while the second to the stability ranking among the tested between treatments (the lowest value is the most stable; while the highest the most instable).

Treatment	Energy (means)	CV	ACV	W Ecovalence	Shukla's stability variance				
ASC1-CA	14.65	53.8	2	57.1	7	539.4	8	42.1	8
ASC1-CT	19.59	66.0	3	70.6	9	1366.7	9	113.0	9
ASC1-ORG	17.93	47.1	1	57.2	8	289.5	6	20.7	6
ASC2-CA	16.6	135.8	8	31.0	1	192.5	4	12.4	4
ASC2-CT	13.96	150.8	9	53.7	6	225.3	5	15.2	5
ASC2-ORG	20.14	90.5	7	41.5	2	123.2	2	6.5	2
NO-CA	10.9	71.1	4	46.3	3	141.4	3	8.0	3
NO-CT	5.84	83.8	5	52.6	5	470.3	7	36.2	7
NO-ORG	16.06	86.3	6	48.5	4	92.3	1	3.8	1

5. Conclusions

Preliminary results of our study suggest that it is possible to redesign more sustainable and diversified farming systems to enhance the provisioning of ecosystem services and the resilience of agroecosystem. In fact, the main findings pointed out that the crop performance may fluctuate from year to year also considering random weather extreme events that can cause serious concerns to the farmers. Thus, the agroecological management practices adopted in the flat strips such as GM-ORG and RC2-ORG or in the ridges such as ASC2-ORG and ASC1-CT can increase the yield energy stability of the crop sequence, because they have the potential to achieve good performances and resilience of the system, especially when the climate conditions are not optimal, or extreme climate events occur.

Nevertheless, the crop species and varieties choice and agroecological management strategies upgrading are crucial to increase the benefits of more sustainable systems.

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